

The Implicit Knowledge Retention Ecosystem: An Information Architecture Analysis

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Abstract

In an organizational setting, a constant stream of implicit knowledge is being created. For example, an organization may have a formal recruitment process to hire candidates - a type of explicit knowledge. However, the effectiveness of the process depends on the recruiter's skills and experience developed over time as they learn how to hire the highest quality candidates. This type of knowledge, acquired from practice and experience, is called implicit knowledge. When key talents like subject matter experts, leaders, or other high-performing individuals leave an organization for any reason, they also take away the implicit knowledge needed to operate at top efficiency and effectiveness. Simultaneously, existing employees who do similar work and desire to increase their skills and knowledge miss out on the implicit knowledge unless exchanged with each other. This is a problem for organizations since new employees, those moving into new leadership positions, or employees doing similar work might not have the ability to access or share implicit knowledge.

Keywords: Implicit Knowledge, Tacit Knowledge, Communities of Practice, Instructional Design, Information Architecture, Knowledge Management, Knowledge Retention, Instructional Design, Systems Thinking, Organization Development

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1. Executive Summary

The purpose of this proposal is to describe Wonder Women's proposed program that will allow clients to capture the implicit knowledge of employees and then share it with the rest of the organization. Our solution is a knowledge capture and transmission strategy with efficient processes for capturing, storing, and distributing the knowledge within the organization. Because of the synergy of many processes working to harvest implicit knowledge, we have named this model "*the implicit knowledge retention ecosystem.*"

2. Definition: Understanding the Problem of Implicit Knowledge

In an organizational setting, there is a constant stream of implicit knowledge being created. For example, an organization may have a formal recruitment process to hire candidates - a type of explicit knowledge. However, the effectiveness of the process depends on the recruiter's skills and experience developed over time as they learn how to hire the highest quality candidates. This type of knowledge, acquired from practice and experience, is called *implicit knowledge*.

When key talents like subject matter experts, leaders, or other high-performing individuals leave an organization for any reason, they also take away the implicit knowledge needed to operate at top efficiency and effectiveness. Simultaneously, existing employees who do similar work and desire to increase their skills and knowledge miss out on the implicit knowledge unless exchanged with each other. This is a problem for organizations, since new employees, those moving into new leadership positions or employees doing similar work might not have the ability to access or share implicit knowledge.

3. Solutions and Implementation Plan

Our solution, called “*the implicit knowledge retention ecosystem*” has two phases and distinct steps within each phase that address all the aspects of implicit knowledge capture and transmission. These solutions are also scalable depending upon the company size and the resources available within an organization. The two phases are summarized below and then detailed in the rest of the proposal.

The Implicit Knowledge Retention Ecosystem

Phase I: Develop the Foundational Infrastructure

1. Identify critical knowledge areas
2. Create policies that support knowledge retention
3. Create motivation strategies

Phase II: Develop Implicit Knowledge Capture, Storage, and Retrieval Processes

1. Communication Campaigns
2. Knowledge Capture Processes
 - Storytelling
 - Apprenticeship
 - After Actions Review
 - Communities of Practice
3. Knowledge Storage & Retrieval Processes
 - Information Architecture

Figure 1: Implicit Knowledge Retention Ecosystem.

To implement the knowledge retention ecosystem, Wonder Women will first discuss the proposed deliverables with the client. The client will have the opportunity to go through the framework to request any customization needed and ensure the proposed product is likely to meet the client’s expectations and desired goals.

Figure 2: Implicit Knowledge Retention Implementation Framework. **Click the image for a larger view.**

PHASE I: DEVELOP FOUNDATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE

Step 1 - Identify Critical Knowledge Areas

The rationale for identifying critical knowledge areas is to help clients assess their existing knowledge base and create a *"Skills Inventory"* that addresses their current and future needs. We will collaborate with the client to identify what type of implicit knowledge should be captured, what type of knowledge is critical for the organization's success, who has the implicit knowledge, and who are the people to whom this knowledge will be delivered. This step will ensure that clients capture, store and spread the right competencies and capabilities across their

organization. This step will help clients to narrow down their focus strategically and utilize their resources optimally.

Implementation Plan

To implement this step, we will conduct a review of the client's existing performance management systems, interview department managers/leaders and conduct a gap analysis to identify what knowledge areas are critical for present and future needs. We will then analyze the data collected to create a "*Skills Inventory*," which will include a comprehensive list of existing competencies, gaps, and key performers from whom the implicit knowledge will be captured.

Deliverables:

- Skills Inventory
- Data Analysis & Report

Step 2 - Create Knowledge Retention Policies

Creating knowledge retention policies is critical for developing an environment where knowledge-sharing behavior becomes part of the organization's culture. In 2002, NASA initiated a culture change program called "One NASA." The program emphasized a unified strategic plan, commitment for teamwork, tools, and capabilities for better collaboration (DeLong, 2004). This culture change program helped NASA create a retention culture that embraced knowledge sharing, adapting existing knowledge bases, and creating new ones.

In order to create such an environment, there must be trust between employers, employees, and different teams in an organization. Wonder Women will work with the client to align their organizational policies to a structure that supports employee trust and generates:

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- knowledge retention culture
- learning culture
- knowledge alignment
- employer empathy
- shared visions
- team unity

Implementation Plan

To implement this step, we will first conduct a culture climate survey to understand whether knowledge retention behavior exists. Second, we will review the client's existing policies and assess the data points generated from the *Culture Climate Report*. It will help the client understand the organizational culture on knowledge retention behavior. We will then collaborate with the HR department to create new or redesign existing policies and procedures that improve the organizational culture and create an environment for knowledge retention.

Deliverables:

- Culture Climate Report
- Policies and Standard Operating Procedures; the policies and procedures will focus on the following:
 1. Create a shared sense of purpose and vision
 2. Identify the big picture for knowledge sharing behavior: who?, what?, why?
 3. Clarify diversity and inclusion's impact on implicit knowledge collection and distribution.

4. Establish a plan for authentic communication around stressful circumstances (such as a layoff) and the organization's commitment to explain what employees will get in return for knowledge sharing. This will help to build trust for implicit knowledge sharing.
5. Explain how eliminating unconscious bias, racism, and discrimination improves equitable knowledge participation

Step 3 - Create Motivation Strategy

The final step in the foundational infrastructure is to think about why an employee would share knowledge and acquire knowledge shared by others. Wonder Women will work with the client to create a motivation strategy that stimulates employees to share and acquire knowledge that is sustainable for the long term. Organizations have used the work of Abraham Maslow, "Maslow's hierarchy of needs", to create benefits packages for their employees. (Maslow, 1943) Maslow's five core needs form the basis for human behavioral motivation, i.e.,

- Physiological needs,
- Safety needs,
- Love and belonging needs,
- Esteem needs, and
- Self-actualization needs

Based on "Maslow's hierarchy of needs," we will create a motivation strategy that supports employees at different levels in the hierarchy of needs and rewards knowledge-sharing behavior.

Implementation Plan

We will consult with the HR representative or an administrator for Compensation and Benefits (if available) to understand the client's current budget, existing performance management systems, and available resources for creating a motivation strategy. Employees might have different needs and priorities based on their professional and personal situations. *We will design and curate a range of Incentive Programs and Career Development Processes that support employee needs at different levels and rewards knowledge retention behavior.* Employees will have the choice and freedom to select from this range of incentives and career development programs.

Deliverables:

- Design document for a Monetary and Non-Monetary Incentive Program
- Design document for a Career Development Program
- Standard Operating Procedures for rolling out the programs

Table 1: Examples of an Incentive Program and Career Development Program

Incentive Program	
Monetary Incentives	Non-Monetary Incentives
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Reward programs for knowledge sharing behavior ● Bonus ● Tuition Fee Coverage (professional education programs, university sponsorship programs). ● Stock Options ● Additional Paid Holidays ● Paid Family Vacations ● Retirement Health Coverage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Certificates of Achievements, Social Recognition Award Programs. ● Flexible Project Selection ● Flexible Work Hours/Work From Home ● Child Care Assistance ● Mental Health Wellness Programs
Career Development Program	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lateral Career Path: Multi-layered career promotion and growth opportunities. ● Job Rotation and Capability Sharing ● Phased Retirement/Flexible Retirement Plans (Especially for high-performing/subject matter experts/skills with a labor shortage at a retirement phase). ● Positions for retiring employees (Example: Consultants/ Freelance Coach/ Part-Time Employment/ Temporary Employment). ● Succession planning for high-performing individuals/ subject matter experts or employees who have critical knowledge. 	

- Knowledge consulting positions for situations like layoffs, downsizing, etc.

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PHASE II: DEVELOP KNOWLEDGE CAPTURE, STORAGE & RETRIEVAL PROCESSES

Step 1: Communications Strategy

Once the above foundational infrastructure is developed, the first step of Phase II will be to develop a **communication strategy** that brings awareness of the knowledge retention ecosystem to employees.

Implementation Plan

We will collaborate with the Human Resources representative to create a robust communication strategy that is best suitable for the client's needs.

Deliverables:

- Awareness Campaign Standard Operating Procedure
- Campaign Materials and Templates

The process documents will include:

1. Awareness Campaigns Materials: Email templates, social media templates, presentation templates, and additional templates for other communication tools.
2. Awareness Campaign Timelines: Strategic timelines for rolling out the awareness campaigns:

Figure 3: Prototype of an awareness campaign template.

Step 2 - Create Knowledge Capture Programs

This is the *core step* where we capture implicit knowledge once we establish the environment supporting the knowledge capturing processes. In this step, we will collaborate with multiple stakeholders like HR, department representatives, IT Specialists (only high-tech environment), administrators as per the client's needs and resource availability. Following are the four programs for capturing knowledge:

- A. Storytelling*
- B. Apprenticeship*
- C. After Actions Review*
- D. Communities of Practice*

A. Storytelling: Storytelling is a powerful tool to make a human-to-human connection by sharing personal experiences. People pass on their accumulated wisdom from experiences naturally through stories. “Research shows that stories are an effective way for transferring both implicit knowledge about how things get done, as well as deeper tacit knowledge that reflects the values shaping behaviors” (DeLong, 2004). We will work with the client to develop a storytelling program through structured talk sessions/podcasts/digital events. In these events, employees from diverse backgrounds will be encouraged to share stories that divulge their professional experiences, knowledge, practice, and thoughts. These stories will be recorded in audio and video formats, then curated and transmitted through the communities of practice and knowledge libraries to ensure equitable access.

Implementation Plan

To kick start the program, the client will have the opportunity to select their internal facilitators who will run the program on an ongoing basis and identify subject matter experts by referring to the “*Skills Inventory*” created in Phase I.

Deliverables:

- Standard Operating Procedure (S.O.P)
- Facilitator Guide

These process documents for both the S.O.P and facilitator guide will include:

1. How to conduct storytelling sessions, interviewing techniques, the **context** for storytelling sessions.

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2. When and how to conduct the storytelling sessions which are consistent and have equitable access for all employees.
3. How to align storytelling sessions with “communities of practice” based on knowledge areas/topic/functional competencies or behavioral competencies.
4. How to have multiple options to both share stories and listen to stories (Example: Podcasts/Events/Townhalls/Community Events/Digital Events).
5. How to record stories (Videos/Audios recorders and/or codify key information)
6. How to feature stories using company-wide communication tools, e.g., bulletins/magazines/intranet/notice board or Content Management Systems/Learning Management Systems (high-tech environments)
7. How to store the knowledge captured in the information architecture library management system which will be built by us.

B. Apprenticeship: Apprenticeship at its core means that employees observe, enact, and practice their mentors’ core behaviors to gain implicit wisdom through experiential learning. This type of mentoring supports sharing the broadest range of knowledge, from detailed technical skills and tacit cultural values to career development advice, in a relationship that ideally allows the expert to monitor the degree to which knowledge is being acquired (DeLong, 2004).

When used strategically, an apprenticeship program can transfer implicit cognitive and behavioral knowledge like technical, operational, or managerial skills. Apprenticeship also helps a protégé learn implicit knowledge i.e. “who does what and how” in an organization. Providing introductions to influential decision-makers and specialized experts helps less experienced

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employees develop the relationships they will need to succeed in an organization. Wonder Women will work with the client to develop an apprenticeship program that includes mentorship opportunities for employees whose tacit knowledge the client wants to pass on to other employees. Wonder Women will provide specific fundamental ways to approach and implement apprenticeship for mentees within the client's organizational setting.

Implementation Plan

We will work with the client to launch the apprenticeship program by identifying the mentors who have critical knowledge. These mentors will be either subject matter experts, highly skilled employees, retiring employees, or leaders who are the best suitable candidates to be a mentor and impart knowledge by referring to the “**Skills Inventory**” created in Phase I. We will work with the client’s department heads & HR to select facilitators who will be responsible for ongoing and consistent program implementation.

Deliverables:

- Standard Operating Procedure (S.O.P)
- Train the Trainer Guide for the mentors
- Facilitator’s Guide

These process documents for S.O.P, trainer guide, and facilitator guide will include:

1. Communications strategy for bringing awareness to both apprentices and mentors about the context behind a mentoring program.
2. Facilitator's guide on when and how to conduct the apprenticeship program which is consistent, and has equitable access for all employees.

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3. The enrollment process on how to select mentors, who will select the mentors and apprentices.
4. Role of the facilitator, mentor, apprentice, and other stakeholders in order to manage and coordinate the apprenticeship program.
5. Mentor guide on how to include multiple ways to mentor an apprentice through observation, shadowing, action learning, or learning by doing.
6. How to record action learning sessions

C. After Action Review: The apprenticeship program is an effective way to transfer implicit knowledge; however, to sustain the results and for learners to embed it in their long-term memory, an "After Action Review" (AAR) is beneficial. AAR provides learners the opportunity to reflect on their learning, integrate it into their on-the-job tasks and activities, and create new knowledge by ideating process improvements. First employed by the U.S. Army (Collison & Parcell, 2004), an After Action Review (AAR) is a focused process that helps groups crystallize and validate new knowledge or learn from a recent event or project they have participated in.

The process is built around four questions:

1. What was supposed to happen?
2. What actually happened?
3. Why were there differences?
4. What can we learn from this and do differently next time?

We will embed the apprenticeship program with AAR to create processes that answer these four fundamental questions so mentees are able to reflect on their learning, integrate it into their on-the-job tasks and activities, and create new knowledge by ideating process improvements.

Implementation Plan

Once an apprenticeship program is rolled out, the next step will be to implement an After Action Review (AAR) program. We will work with the stakeholders to align the “After Action Review” program with the Apprenticeship program.

Deliverables:

- Standard Operating Procedure (S.O.P)
- Facilitator’s Guide

These process documents for both S.O.P and facilitator guide will include:

1. How to create a “reflection activity” for apprentices to reflect on their learning.
2. Timing for the reflection activity, and facilitator’s role.
3. Facilitator’s guide on auditing on-the-job practice sessions for apprentices to implement knowledge learned and have hands-on experience.
4. Roles of the apprentice and mentor in the AAR program.
5. How to store knowledge captured and new knowledge created in the information architecture.

D. Communities of Practice: Communities of Practice (C.O.P) is an effective program used to connect people with *specialized sources of information and construct knowledge together* in a community format. C.O.P has its roots in the theories of connectivism and constructivism. Constructivism suggests that learners create knowledge as they attempt to understand their experiences (Driscoll, 2000, p. 376). In comparison, connectivism suggests the integration of networks, connecting specialized information sets, and the connections that enable us to learn

more than our current state of knowing. C.O.P will help the client to capture implicit knowledge from subject matter experts, solve problems more quickly, transfer best practices, develop professional skills amongst its employees, and help retain talent. Procter & Gamble (P&G), a global consumer goods manufacturing corporation, has used communities of practice extensively over a wide range of disciplines. This has helped P&G in the identification, development, and deployment of new research methodology, and improved problem-solving on specific projects (Archer, 2003). We will work with the client to create C.O.P groups and processes for knowledge sharing through both in-person and digital collaborations to engage expert practitioners who have implicit knowledge with others throughout the organization.

Implementation Plan

In order to launch the C.O.P program, we will consult with multiple stakeholders at the client's organization to identify technical/functional skills and behavioral skills that are most important for the client by referring to the "Skills Inventory." For example, some communities of practices can be formed based on the "Skills Inventory."

1. Software Programming
2. Quality Control (Q.C)
3. Customer Service
4. Sales and Marketing
5. Communications Skills
6. Negotiation and Networking

Then, we will work with the client to create C.O.P Skill Groups which will include a "core group." This core group will be responsible for leading the community of practice in

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collaboration with their member base. The core group will be responsible for organizing and hosting all the events/projects, for example, directing community events such as storytelling sessions and town halls.

Deliverables:

- Anti-bias recruitment process for core group members for ensuring equitable access to all employees
- Standard Operating Procedure (S.O.P)
- Core Group Guide
- Facilitator Guide
- Participant Guide

These process documents for S.O.P, recruitment process, core-group guide, participant guide and facilitator guide will include:

- Who should be included in C.O.P groups, and how to ensure equitable access
- Who should be a part of the core group, and the role of core group members, participant members, and group members.
- The enrollment process and how to invite employees to join a community of practice groups. Rules for joining multiple groups.
- What do participants need to do to stay in the group?
- How to create multiple pathways for creating in-person as well as digital C.O.P groups that meet client needs in both low-tech and high-tech environments.
- How to codify knowledge captured in C.O.P groups, who will codify it, the role of other stakeholders, and how to embed codified knowledge in the information architecture.

Step 3: Knowledge Storage and Retrieval

This is the final step where implicit knowledge is stored and retrieved. Wonder Women will design and develop a knowledge library using an *information architecture* that is easily retrievable, curated as per learner needs, and easy to manage. We offer a flexible information architecture that is scalable and buildable to suit the needs of a *low-tech as well as a high-tech environment*. The core principles for both these environments will remain the same: make it easy to create and manage. For a low-tech environment, we will create a manual library management information architecture using either a physical library with file management and indexing system or a manual computer with a shared drive system.. And, for a high-tech environment, we propose to create an information architecture that uses an LMS (Learning Management System) or a CMS (Content Management System), or any other existing LMS or CMS platform. To meet the client's needs and budget, we can add additional features like A.I (Artificial Intelligence) and Adaptive Learning Technologies to automate storing of captured knowledge, content delivery by adapting to learner needs and providing curated content for an effective learning experience.

Implementation Plan

Following is our implementation plan for *storing and retrieving* implicit knowledge:

Figure 4: Information Architecture of a low-tech and high-tech environment. **Click image for a larger view**

A Library Storage System will be created by us that allows employers to store the information that is obtained in the previous solutions. For example, after a storytelling session is produced, a “Library Storage System” will support employers in retaining the information and making it accessible to their employee base.

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Depending on the size and investment of the employer we have low-tech to high-tech storage and retrieval system options. The differences between low-tech and high-tech solutions will be in the nature of tools that are used for the deployment and retrieval of knowledge. For the *low-tech* option, it can be the following:

1. Convert data into instructional content using a manual approach like paper-based instructional content in organizations where technology is at a very basic level or seldom used. Data can also be converted into a Microsoft word document that organizes the information. We will provide an administrative manual for converting data into instructional content for future use.
2. Deploy content into an accessible shared system like a physical library with file management and indexing system or a manual computer with a shared drive system.
3. Assign content to employees through providing access to documents/videos/audios.

For the *high-tech* option, the tools that are used for each step can be as follows:

1. Convert data into instructional content through course authoring software and video/audio editing tools. We will provide an administrative manual for converting data into instructional content for future use.
2. Deploy content on the CMS/LMS system
3. Assign content to appropriate employees using A.I and Adaptive technologies (optional).

Deliverables:

- Standard operating procedure (S.O.P)
- User Manual
- Content integration manual for CMS or LMS: Only for high-tech environment

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- Physical Library Management Manual or Computer-based Library Management Manual (low-tech)
- Digital Library Management Manual (high-tech)

These process documents for S.O.P, as well as all the manuals will include:

1. How to **Store** Data on the internal hard drive, external hard drive, or cloud storage systems
2. How to **Convert** Data into instructional content in line with adult learning methodologies, including the use of an outline, sections, library indexing systems, and categories that organize contents for consumption.
3. How to **Deploy** content through a platform, or space that is accessible to employees. It could be a physical office library, a manual computer-based library, or a high-tech digital library.
4. How to **Assign** relevant content to employees.
5. How to **Update** content.

4. Resource Requirements

The resources needed for developing and implementing the implicit knowledge retention ecosystem will depend on the size and resources available with an organization. We will first meet the stakeholders in the very beginning to understand their needs, budget, and available resources to further provide details about what resources we will need to both capture implicit knowledge as well as pooling the information and making it available to employees in a usable format. The following is an example of resources needed **from the client**:

1. Human Capital Requirements: (for all environments)

- Client's internal program owners: Human Resources Representatives, Subject Matter Experts depending upon the various departments, size of the organization, Facilitator responsible for program implementation and Administrator for curating and maintaining knowledge library. **Internal positions are at the client's discretion.**
- Wonder Women program owners: 2 Internal Staff, 1 IT Specialist (high-tech), 1 User Tester.

2. Technical Requirements

- **Low-Tech Environment:**
 - Technical Requirements: Client's existing systems.
 - Hardware Requirements: Video Camera/Phone, Computer/Laptops (if available), Audio Recorder, Television if a computer is unavailable.
- **High-Tech Environment:**
 - Technical Requirements: CMS like SharePoint/Salesforce CMS **or** LMS like Adobe Prime or any other CMS/LMS system, collaboration tools that can be integrated into the CMS or LMS like Slack. A.I tools to automate content curation and adapt to learner needs (if an organization opts for it).
 - Hardware Requirements: Video Camera/Phone, Laptops, Audio Recorder, Digital audio recording/video recording like Zoom. Computer or cloud memory storage.

The following are the **deliverables** from **Women Women**:

- S.O.P: Standard operating procedures for all the phases of implementation

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- Media: Administrative manual for converting data into instructional content(Audio/Video/Documents).
- Content integration manual for CMS or LMS (high-tech)
- Knowledge Library Manuals for both environments

5. Development Strategy

In the development stage, we will use an agile process, i.e., the successive approximation model (S.A.M), to make iterations continually to elicit continuous feedback and build working models earlier in the process. The idea behind an iterative development phase will be to shorten the design and development review cycles and provide a framework for multiple stakeholders to collaborate effectively. Following is the **project plan** for developing the knowledge retention ecosystem.

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PROJECT PLAN

PROJECT PLAN : IMPLICIT KNOWLEDGE RETENTION ECOSYSTEM											
		PROJECT TITLE	START DATE								
		Implicit Knowledge Retention Ecosystem	1st August, 2021		PROJECT DURATION in days						
		PROJECT OWNERS	END DATE								
WONDER WOMEN:		Wonder Women Staff 1 and 2, 1 IT Specialist, 1 User Tester	15th January, 2022		314 DAYS						
CLIENT:		HR, Administrator, Facilitator, Department Managers/Leaders								MILESTONES	
PHASES	WBS NO.	TASKS	STATUS	DURATION in hours	AUGUST, 2021	SEPTEMBER, 2021	OCTOBER, 2021	NOVEMBER, 2021	DECEMBER, 2021	JANUA 2022	
PROJECT PREPARATION	1	PREPARATION PHASE	Not Started	21	8/15/2021						
	1.1	- Requirement Gathering from Client		2							
	1.2	- Meeting with Project Team & User Research		3							
	1.3	- Project Scope		2							
	1.4	- Budget Finalization		2							
	1.5	- Resources and Staffing Needs Analysis		2							
	1.6	- Key Performance Indicators List & Goal Setting		3							
	1.7	- Client Instructional Systems Design Analysis Report		6							
	1.8	- Project Kickoff Meeting and Project Initiation		1							
DEVELOP FOUNDATIONAL INFRASTRUCTURE	2	DESIGN PHASE	Not Started	45		9/5/2021					
PROJECT PLANNING	2.1	- High Level Design/ Flow Charts for the Knowledge Ecosystem		7							
	2.2	- KPIs and Goal Setting		2							
ITERATIVE DESIGN & PROTOTYPE	2.3	- Identify Critical Knowledge		10							
	2.4	- Create Retention Policies		10							
	2.5	- Create Motivation Strategy		7							
REVIEW	2.6	- Review & Testing		4							
	3	DEVELOPMENT PHASE	Not Started	80		10/31/2021					
DESIGN PROOF	3.1	- Development Scope		4							
DEVELOP	3.2	- Identify Critical Knowledge: *Employee Interviews *Audit existing Performance Reports *Data Analysis & Report *Create "Skills Inventory"		26							
	3.3	- Create Retention Policies: *Culture Climate Report *Audit existing Policies *Redesign existing policies, or		26							
	3.4	- Create Motivation Strategy: *Design Incentive Programs *Design Career Development Programs		20							
EVALUATE	3.5	- Quality Assurance and Testing		4							
DEVELOP KNOWLEDGE CAPTURE STORAGE											

Figure 5: Project Plan. Click image for Excel Sheet.

6. Budget

Table 2: Estimated budget

*IT Specialist is required only for the high-tech environment.

Preparation Phase				
Deliverables	Hourly Rate	Estimated Hours	Number of Staff	Total Cost
Deliverables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project Scope Key Performance Indicators List) Client Instructional Systems Design Analysis Report 	\$100	21	Wonder Women Staff 1 & 2	\$4200
Total				\$4200
Phase 1: Develop Foundational Infrastructure				
Step1: Identify Critical Knowledge Areas: Deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Analysis & Report Skills Inventory Tasks involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employee Interviews (5 department managers/leaders) Audit existing performance reports (Past 2 years report) 	\$100	15 hours	2	\$3000
Total				\$3000
Step 2: Create Retention Policies: Deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Culture Climate Survey Report Retention Policies and Standard Operating Processes Tasks involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Culture Climate Survey Audit existing policies Redesign existing policies, or 	\$100	30 hours	2	\$6000 for survey and audit Additional \$6000 for redesigning policies Or,

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create new policies & processes (optional) 				* \$10000 for crafting new policies
Total				\$12000 or \$16000
Step 3: Create Motivation Strategy: Deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design document for Incentive Programs • Design document for Career Development Programs • Standard Operating Procedures Tasks Involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Audit client's current compensation and benefits budget, existing performance management systems, and resource analysis 	\$100	80 hours	2	\$16000
Total				\$16000
Phase 2: Communication Strategy, Knowledge Capture, Storage and Retrieval				
Step1: Communication Strategy: Deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Awareness Campaign Standard Operating Procedure • Campaign Materials and Templates 	\$100	20 hours	2	\$4000
Total				\$4000
Step 2: Knowledge Capture: Deliverables <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storytelling: Standard Operating Procedure, and Facilitator Guide. • Apprenticeship: Standard Operating Procedure, Facilitator Guide, Train the Trainer Guide. • After Actions Review: Standard Operating Procedure and Facilitator Guide. 	\$100	Wonder Women: 100 hours	(Wonder Women Staff 1 and 2),	\$20000
	IT Specialist \$50	IT Specialist: 100 hours	1 IT Specialist	\$5000

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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communities of Practice: Standard Operating Procedure, and Facilitator Guide, Core Group Guide, the anti-bias recruitment process for core group members, Participant Guide. 	User Tester \$50	User Tester: 20 hours	1 User Tester	\$1000
Total				\$21000 and \$5000 additional for IT Specialist)
<p>Step 3: Knowledge Storage & Retrieval: Deliverables</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Information Architecture ● Standard operating procedures ● Maintenance Guide <p>Tasks involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● System setup & deployment ● Testing 	<p>\$100 each for Wonder Women Staff 1 and 1.</p> <p>IT Specialist \$50</p> <p>User Tester \$50</p>	<p>Wonder Women: 100 hours</p> <p>IT Specialist: 100 hours</p> <p>User Tester: 50 hours</p>	<p>(Wonder Women Staff 1 and 2),</p> <p>1 IT Specialist</p> <p>1 User Tester</p>	<p>\$20000</p> <p>\$5000</p> <p>\$2500</p>
Total				\$22500, and \$5000 additional for IT Specialist)

ArPHASE II PROPOSAL FOR AECT-NATO ACT

Evaluation				
<p>Deliverables:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evaluation Reports <p>Tasks involved:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reaction Analysis- Alpha Release Learning Analysis - Beta Release Behavior Analysis- Gold Release 	<p>\$100 each for Wonder Women Staff 1 and 1.</p> <p>IT Specialist \$50</p> <p>User Tester \$50</p>	<p>Wonder Women: 100 hours</p> <p>IT Specialist: 100 hours</p> <p>User Tester: 100 hours</p>	<p>(Wonder Women Staff 1 and 2),</p> <p>1 IT Specialist</p> <p>1 User Tester</p>	<p>\$20000</p> <p>\$5000</p> <p>\$5000</p>
				<p>\$25000 and \$5000 additional for IT Specialist)</p>
Client's Internal Project Members	At the client's discretion.			
<p>Resource Requirements</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authoring Tool CMS/LMS for high-tech environment Video recorder/Camera recorder Miscellaneous 				<p>\$10000 (high-tech), and \$5000 (other expenses)</p>
Total Investment for Low- Tech Environment	\$112700			
Total Investment for High-Tech Environment	\$137700			
*Additional for crafting new policies in Phase I, step 2	\$10000			

7. Evaluation Strategy

We will integrate the client's existing evaluation processes or create new processes with the Kirkpatrick model to evaluate the degree of targeted outcomes. The Kirkpatrick Model (Allen, 2012) is a globally recognized method of evaluating the results of learning programs. The evaluation process of the Kirkpatrick model is divided into four levels, i.e., **reaction, learning, behavior, and results**. Following is our strategy to evaluate program success based on these four levels.

- **Reaction:** We will review the reaction of employees after the **Alpha** release of the implicit knowledge retention ecosystem. This is the stage where we will work with the client and program owners to create a survey to capture employee reactions.
- **Learning:** We will assess the learning phase after the **Beta** release. In this phase, we will create a process to evaluate the expertise and knowledge gained by employees, using interviews and assessments with apprentices/peers and mentors.
- **Behavior:** We will assess the behavior phase after the **Gold** release. In this phase, we will create a process to evaluate if implicit knowledge gained by employees was implemented at the workplace. Our deliverables will include a process that integrates the client's performance management systems, LMS analytics (high-tech), After Actions Review Reports, and 360-degree feedback by taking feedback from multiple stakeholders.
- **Results:** To evaluate the overall success of the knowledge ecosystem, we will work with the client to create a KPI (Key Performance Indicator) system such as quality control data, Diversity & Inclusion representations in Communities of Practice, safety records, production times, and sales conversion, etc.

Arpita Pal, Alyssa Thomas AECT-NATO ACT

8. Prototypes

- [Sample Skills Inventory](#)
- Sample Facilitator Guide Overview of Communities of Practice:

Facilitator's Guide

Communities of Practice

Table of Contents

1. [How to use the facilitator guide?](#)
2. [What are Communities of Practice?](#)
3. [Core Member Recruitment Process](#)
4. [Community Agenda](#)
5. [Member Enrollment Process](#)
6. [Anti-Bias, Ethics, and Equity Policy](#)
 - Introduction
 - Module 1
 - Module 2
 - Module 3
 - Wrap-Up

VILT PPT Presentation Instructions

Slide/Topic/Time	Visuals	Instructions
Landing Slide 1 Minute		START the session at least 5 minutes early to allow participants to join the virtual conference tool. OPEN PowerPoint Presentation. DISPLAY this title slide as participants enter the VILT Session. BEGIN the session at an exact time. It's crucial to start the session on time to cover all topics. INTRODUCE yourself. WELCOME the participants and announce the course is beginning. ASK PARTICIPANTS to use the Chat section to introduce each other.
Slide 2 Training Agenda		DISPLAY SLIDE 2 EXPLAIN that participants are expected to engage in this interactive session, especially during activities (like a face-to-face course). Explain how to use the

Figure 6: Facilitator Guide

- Sample Knowledge Retention Ecosystem Infographic:

Figure 7: Knowledge Retention Ecosystem Infographic. *Click image for larger view

- Sample Knowledge Retrieval Design of a low-tech and high-tech knowledge library.

Figure 8: Knowledge Retrieval Design. *Click image for larger view

9. Reference

- Allen, M. (2012). Leaving ADDIE for SAM: Faster, Better Learning Product Development. American Society for Training & Development.
- Archer, N. (2003). SOME PERSPECTIVES ON COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE. Retrieved from <https://macsphere.mcmaster.ca/bitstream/11375/5435/1/fulltext.pdf>
- Collison, C., & Parcell, G. (2004). Learning to fly: practical knowledge management from some of the world's leading learning organizations (2nd ed.). Capstone.
- DeLong, D. (2004). Lost Knowledge: Confronting the Threat of an Aging Workforce. : Oxford University Press. Retrieved 2 Jul. 2021, from <https://oxford-universitypressscholarship-com.jpallnet.sfsu.edu/view/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780195170979.001.0001/acprof-9780195170979>.
- Driscoll, M.P (2006). Psychology of learning for instruction, 3rd edition. Pearson Education, Inc.
- Maslow, A. H. (1943). A theory of human motivation. Psychological Review, 50(4), 370–396. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0054346>